

Experimental Study of Optimal Antenna Array Configuration for Non-invasive UWB Microwave Temperature Monitoring during Hyperthermia

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Abstract—Temperature monitoring during thermal therapies is used to regulate the amount of heat distributed to the cancerous tissue and therefore improve the clinical outcome of the oncological treatment. For the development of a hybrid hyperthermia system with non-invasive temperature monitoring by means of ultra-wideband (UWB) imaging, the optimal configuration of sensing antennas and heating applicators has to be investigated. In this paper we present the results of numerical simulations of several possible antenna arrangements, which are then validated by experiments with the radar system. The performance of each channel configuration was analyzed and benefits for the different clinical scenarios were specified.

Keywords—hybrid microwave system, hyperthermia, ultra-wideband, non-invasive temperature monitoring

I. INTRODUCTION

It is well-known that thermal therapies are used as support therapies for oncological treatment. One of its applications, microwave hyperthermia, heats the tumorous tissue up to 44 °C to make it accessible for the radiation, increase response to the drugs and improve the clinical outcome of the conventional cancer treatment – radiotherapy and chemotherapy [1]. Accurate temperature monitoring of the area to be treated is required to provide precise heating to all cancerous cells without damage of the healthy ones. The application of hyperthermia in the neck region (esophagus, larynx, thyroid gland, trachea and lymph nodes cancer) with current invasive temperature control applications is, firstly, painful for the patient, and secondly, not always possible due to the clinical restrictions on their placement as well as due to the complex structure of the neck. One of the alternative solutions can be non-invasive temperature monitoring by means of microwave ultra-wideband (UWB) imaging. This method aims to estimate the temperature of the biological tissue based on the changes of its dielectric properties [2].

Microwave UWB imaging should be included into microwave hyperthermia system to provide reliable and exceptional real-time non-invasive temperature monitoring

during the treatment. The development of such a hybrid microwave system brings several challenges, specifically, the limited space for positioning of the sensing antennas due to quite large dimensions of the heating applicators and relatively small dimensions of the neck region. In the real clinical hyperthermia scenario, rotation of the antenna array like in [2] will not be possible, which leads to a significant reduction of the amount of measurement channels. To achieve the best possible imaging resolution, optimal antenna configuration has to be defined.

In this work, we present the results of the investigations of different arrangements of dipole sensing antennas for practical treatment scenarios with the consideration of hyperthermia waveguide applicators placement [3]. In the first step, several arrangements using Sim4Life® simulation platform are numerically tested. The simulated model represents our experimental measurement setup of a simplified phantom mimicking human neck with a tumor. The antenna array allows us to vary the positioning of the sensing antennas as well as to imitate the presence of the hyperthermia applicators by leaving the slots empty. Furthermore, based on the outcome of the numerical study, experiments with multiple input multiple output (MIMO) M-sequence radar system are performed. Then simulated and experimental results are compared. Based on the accuracy of tumor reconstruction in the UWB images we can specify appropriate system configurations.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Methodology

The methodology for non-invasive temperature monitoring via radar-based technology is described in detail in our paper [2]. The pre-treatment part includes creation of the reference dielectric map of the initial treatment state based on the clinical images of another modality (computer tomography, magnetic resonance imaging) and the knowledge of the temperature dependency of specific tissues. The main part is represented by ongoing UWB measurements and imaging. Since UWB imaging is qualitative, estimation of the dielectric properties which can be converted to temperature values is required. Based on the differences between tumorous and surrounding healthy tissues, we calculate the reflection

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coefficient and image the initial scenario. When referring the images of the ongoing measurements to the initial one along with the corresponding reflection coefficients, the permittivity of the tumor region will be estimated [2].

B. Towards the development of the hybrid system

As was mentioned above, the application of the hyperthermia treatment with non-invasive temperature monitoring in the relatively small neck area states a problem of significantly reduced space for antennas placement. The average human neck parameters are: height 10–11 cm, diameter 10–13 cm [4]. To provide efficient and accurate heating to the tumorous tissue, we plan to use three hyperthermia waveguide applicators with strip line horn aperture [3]. In this case the middle applicator should be placed directly in front of the tumor and provide the main amount of heat, while the other two applicators, shifted to the left and to the right, after phase and amplitude optimization will improve heat focusing in the tumorous region. The photo of the waveguide applicator is presented in Fig. 1. The dimensions of the front membrane of the waveguide are 10 cm by 5 cm. Due to the average neck height as well as the applicator height, it is not possible to place the sensing antennas above or below the hyperthermia applicators. This leads us to approximately 40% of the neck circumference for the hyperthermia applicators, 50% for sensing antennas and 10% is left for the adaption of the system to different neck diameters.

C. Measurement setup

The experimental setup for microwave imaging is based on a UWB MIMO M-sequence radar (please find the full description of this technology in [5]) and an array of dipole antennas. The baseband MIMO radar device has a bandwidth 6.5 GHz and includes 8 transmitters and 16 receivers, which results in 128 channels. The bow-tie antennas, implemented on FR4 printed circuit board substrate (0.8 mm) with dimensions of 10 mm by 5.6 mm, are differentially fed by passive baluns.

The neck phantom is inserted in the three-dimensional (3D) printed corpus with 64 slots for antennas and includes two cylinders of radiuses 6.6 and 6.5 cm and heights 11 and 10.8 cm respectively, matching medium layer of a thickness of 0.8 mm placed between corpus and outer cylinder, liquid material under test (MUT) mimicking average neck dielectric properties and a plastic lab tube (\varnothing 1.5 cm, volume 12 mL) filled with tumor mimicking material. The corpus is printed from polylactic acid (PLA) and has cylindrical inner shape and 16-sided polygonal outer shape for exact antennas placement. The 24 passive bow-tie dipole antennas are placed in direct contact with the matching layer, which is produced from silicone and carbon mixture and provides better antenna connection to the outer cylinder as well as unifies the antenna crosstalk. The 3D printed cylinder of bigger diameter is fixed and is in direct contact with matching medium layer as well, while the smaller cylinder is filled with MUT_{bg} and is removable. The tube is inserted in front of the central waveguide which corresponds to sides 8 and 9 ($x = 0.5$ cm, $y = -2.3$ cm). The photo of the experimental setup is presented in Fig. 2.

For the neck phantom we use liquid background medium MUT_{bg} (cream) of complex permittivity $33.2 - i5.4$ at 2 GHz. Due to emulsion of fat and water, cream is well suited for mimicking the dielectric properties of average neck tissue in

Fig. 1. Photo of the water filled hyperthermia waveguide applicator with strip line horn aperture.

Fig. 2. Measurement setup for microwave UWB imaging including: corpus with 64 slots for antennas, cylinder with MUT_{bg} and tube with MUT_t .

microwave frequency range [6, 7]. For tumor phantom MUT_t , we use mixture of distilled water and pure acetone (99.8%) in concentration of 30 vol% acetone, so that its complex permittivity is equal to $64.6 - i11.2$ at 2 GHz.

D. Simulation parameters

Numerical simulation is a crucial step in hybrid microwave system development. We use software platform Sim4Life® for the numerical simulations of our measurement scenario. The capabilities of this software allow to create an accurate biological model including its dielectric properties, define UWB sources, adapt the mesh and voxelization for each part of the simulation model and calculate the electromagnetic field distribution via Finite-Difference Time-Domain method. Our model exactly corresponds to the measurement setup described above. The source signal is chosen as Gaussian modulated pulse in the bandwidth of the radar used in measurements. Mesh and respectively voxelization process was defined separately with different priorities for three regions: neck (big mesh elements, low priority), tumor (middle mesh elements, high priority) and antennas (small mesh elements, middle priority). Choice of the voxels size has strong influence on the accuracy of the solver calculation as well as on the computational time. Full model voxelization consists of 32 MCells. The 64 dipole antennas are placed in correspondence with the 3D printed measurement setup: evenly distributed in four rings on height -2, -4, -6 and -8 cm, with 16 antennas in each ring. This kind of the simulation setting provides an opportunity to avoid computation of all possible antenna arrangements separately and run only one full simulation. The results of this simulation can be then exported and used to study any antenna placement

without performing additional simulations which is very time efficient.

E. Antenna arrangements

Before taking into the consideration the hybrid system scenario, we tested two general ways of arranging the 8 transmitting and the 16 receiving antennas in the mentioned above measurement setup, which are circular and cluster placements. Antenna placement maps of these two arrangements and their simulation based UWB images are shown in Fig. 3. The placement map represents the schematic of the unfolded 3D printed corpus with 16 sides and 64 slots for antennas. Slots filled with blue color represent transmitting antennas and orange color slots indicate receiving ones. As we can see from the UWB images in Fig. 3, both configurations can successfully locate the tumor in the neck phantom, however, circular placement definitely provides an advantage in accuracy of the target reconstruction in the horizontal xy-plane due to the full radial coverage of the phantom with antennas, while cluster arrangement receives more information about target height (xz- and yz-planes) due to the placement of the dipoles on the full column height and close to the target position.

These features can be advantageous depending on location, size and shape of each individual tumor in different clinical scenarios. Head and neck cancers include cancers in the oral cavity (lips, mouth and salivary glands), nasal cavity and paranasal sinus and oropharyngeal cancer. The cancers located in the throat such as cancer of the esophagus, larynx, thyroid gland, trachea and their metastasis in the lymph nodes are related to the neck cancer. Generally, the tumors of the thyroid and larynx have shape close to a sphere or an ellipse and size around 1 to 4 cm depending on the stage, while the esophagus tumors are prolonged and can have length from 3 up to 7 cm. In case of metastasis in the lymph nodes the tumors have commonly spherical shape with diameter of 1–2 cm on early stages and 3–6 cm on late ones [8, 9].

Nevertheless, as was mentioned in section II.B, we have to leave 40% in the radial dimension for hyperthermia applicators. Based on the dimensions of the hyperthermia waveguide, space equal to two sides of the corpus is enough for each applicator, which concludes to 6 sides (24 slots) of the corpus for the hyperthermia part (represented in green color in the antenna placement maps). Taking this into account, circular arrangement is not possible for the hybrid system. As for the cluster arrangement, technically, the hyperthermia and the sensing parts can be placed on the opposite sides of the neck, but this will lead to a low signal level of the sensing antennas (in case when hyperthermia part is placed in front of the tumor) or the heat amount distributed from the applicators will be lower than it is required for the hyperthermia treatment and can spread to the organs in the neck area like spinal cord, which is dangerous for the patient (in case when sensing part is placed in front of the tumor). Based on these requirements, there are 4 main possible symmetric antenna array configurations for the hybrid microwave system: placing three hyperthermia applicators together and using the remaining space for the sensing part or using one, two or three sides of the corpus between the applicators for the sensing antennas. These four basic possible configurations are presented in Fig 4, where the yellow color indicates the slots which can be used for the placement of the sensing antennas.

Fig. 3. Antenna placement maps (Tx: blue, Rx: orange) of circular (a) and cluster (b) arrangement and their UWB images of the phantom with the tumor in xy-slice, $z = -5$ cm and yz-slice, $x = 0.5$ cm. Color bar represents the intensity of the image in the arbitrary units. Dashed white line specify the tumor positions and dimensions.

Fig. 4. Four basic ways to arrange antennas with the consideration of the hyperthermia part. The green color indicates slots for the hyperthermia applicators, the yellow color shows free slots for the sensing antennas.

To meet the requirements of the hyperthermia system and to take advantage of target reconstruction of both circular and cluster configurations, it is necessary to place most sensing antennas close to the target but have several antennas in the circumference of the phantom. After the numerical investigation of different possible combinations of hyperthermia waveguides and sensing antennas in one setup, we present three arrangements appropriate for the neck tumors, which are then implemented in the experimental setup. The different arrangements of antennas are named and numerated as channel configurations (i.e. ChCnf1). ChCnf1 is based on the first type of arrangement, ChCnf2 is based on the second type and ChCnf3 is corresponding to the fourth type (Fig. 4). The investigated channel configurations for the hybrid microwave system are presented in Fig. 5. We do not present in the results part channel configuration based on the third type, since it is an intermediate configuration between ChCnf2 and ChCnf3.

Fig. 5. Antenna placement maps of the investigated arrangements.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Imaging results

After antenna crosstalk removal by means of subtraction of the simulation/measurement without tumor from the data with tumor presence, we apply time-domain beamforming algorithm Delay and Sum to generate the 3D images of numerical and measured data. Since the measurement signal is created by cross correlation between received measurement signal and ideal M-sequence, the amplitude unit is arbitrary. The imaging domain has dimensions from -6.5 to 6.5 cm in x- and y-axis and from -10 to 0 cm in z-axis, the resolution step is equal to 1 mm for all dimensions. The simulation and experiment based UWB images of three studied arrangements are presented in Fig 6 (a) and (b) respectively. As we can see from the Fig. 6 (b), in case of measurement all three channel configurations are able to reconstruct the tube not in its full volume, moreover, due to the difference in antenna placement, each configuration is better performing at different phantom height (images in the yz-plane). For this reason, the images from experiments in the horizontal xy-plane are presented at

three depths specific for every arrangement: $z = -6.1$ cm for ChCnf1, $z = -3.8$ cm for ChCnf2 and $z = -5.4$ cm for ChCnf3. In ChCnf1 the hyperthermia waveguides are placed together in front of the target while the sensing antennas are located only on the sides, therefore the signal level is relatively low.

Fig 6. UWB images of the phantom with the tumor for three studied arrangements in xy-slice and yz-slice, $x = 0.5$ cm, (a) based on the simulation ($z = -5$ cm) and (b) based on the experiment. Color bar represents the intensity of the image in the arbitrary units. Dashed white line specify the tumor positions and dimensions.

Thus, the microwave imaging results of the simulated as well as of the experimental data are not very accurate in both orientations, especially for the measured data. ChCnf2 provides better diversity of the height of antenna placement, additionally this arrangement has two columns of dipoles between the waveguides, so that four transmitters are positioned close to the tumor and other four are 67.5° offset. Receivers are distributed on the whole available circumference of the cylindrical phantom to provide good resolution in the horizontal plane as well. The tumor is located correct based on simulated and measured data but have small symmetric artefacts along the target axis in the xy-plane. From the numerical results it is expected that this channel configuration is able to provide better target reconstruction in vertical orientation ($z = -2.5 : -7.5$ cm), but in the experimental results we can see the part of the tube only in the range $z = -1.5 : -4.5$ cm. The last channel configuration leaves 24 slots between the hyperthermia applicators free for the positioning of the sensing part. Thus, all eight transmitting antennas and majority of the receiving ones are located between waveguides at four available heights in a close to a cluster arrangement way. However, assumed from the images in Fig 3 (a) and the advantages of the circular arrangement, six receivers are also placed in the extreme sides of the phantom. From three studied arrangements, ChCnf3 provides most accurate tube reconstruction in the horizontal plane in both numerical and measured cases. As for the vertical plane, simulation based image corresponds to the one from the experiment well, the depth of the visible reconstruction is similar: $z = -4 : -6$ cm for the simulation and $z = -4.5 : -8$ cm for the measurement.

Certainly, the numerical results are more informative and error-free for all channel configurations, but this can be easily explained by the fact that the simulation is a representation of the ideal experiment: without noise, measurement uncertainties, influence of the presence of PLA cylinders for MUT_{bg} , plastic tube for the MUT_t and matching layer between sensing antennas and neck phantom.

B. Influence of the tumor shape and size

Furthermore, we performed a set of separate simulations with the same settings as described in II.D including the neck phantom, three investigated arrangements (ChCnf1, ChCnf2 and ChCnf3) and three clinically determined tumors. The goal of these simulations is to check the capabilities of the arrangements to locate different targets and to specify which channel configuration is more advantageous in a certain clinical treatment case. In the first simulation, the tumor has a spherical shape and a diameter of 2 cm and can mimic early stage cancer of thyroid gland, larynx or lymph node cancer. In the second scenario, the target is also a sphere but with a diameter of 4 cm and represents thyroid cancer on late stages. Finally, the target of the third case corresponds to esophagus cancer and has a cylindrical shape with a height of 4 cm and a diameter of 2 cm. All three targets are centered at position $x = 0.6$ cm, $y = -3$ cm, $z = -5$ cm. UWB images of these three scenarios for three channel configurations are presented in Fig. 7-9.

Fig 7. UWB images of three studied arrangements with small sphere in xy-slice, $z = -5$ cm and yz-slice, $x = 0.6$ cm. Color bar represents the intensity of the image in the arbitrary units. Dashed white line specify the tumor positions and dimensions.

Fig 8. UWB images of three studied arrangements with big sphere in xy-slice, $z = -5$ cm and yz-slice, $x = 0.6$ cm. Color bar represents the intensity of the image in the arbitrary units. Dashed white line specify the tumor positions and dimensions.

Fig 9. UWB images of three studied arrangements with cylinder in xy -slice, $z = -5$ cm and yz -slice, $x = 0.6$ cm. Color bar represents the intensity of the image in the arbitrary units. Dashed white line specify the tumor positions and dimensions.

As we can see from the images in Fig. 7-9, the simulation with unlike tumors underlines well the strong and the weak points of each arrangement. All channel configurations have fully or particularly reconstructed each of three simulated tumors, but when we look at the spatial distribution of the antennas in the sides of the corpus (Fig. 2), it is quite obvious that in ChCnf1 all antennas are “behind” the tumorous target and as follows the simulated signal is reflected from the “back” side of the tumor and leads to partial image of the target. Similar situation can be mentioned in ChCnf3, where majority of sensing antennas are located “in front” of the tumor. It works really well with smaller targets, but provides only partial (front part of the tumor) reconstruction of the big sphere with diameter of 4 cm. The most accurate reconstruction results are based on ChCnf2 since in this configuration antennas are present both “in front” of the target and “behind” it. In case of the small tumor, the image reconstructed from ChCnf2 is a bit less accurate in comparison to ChCnf3. However, only in this configuration we can see in Fig. 8 the outline of the big sphere, as well as the cylinder in Fig. 9.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents initial investigations towards development of a prototype for microwave hyperthermia system with non-invasive tissue temperature monitoring via

UWB technology. Three different channel configurations were investigated numerically and then tested experimentally. Based on the imaging results from the full simulation and the following measurement data, it is possible to say that the first arrangement of sensing antennas and heating applicators ChCnf1 is not well suitable for the further investigations due to very limited imaging possibilities. Contrariwise, ChCnf2 and ChCnf3 performed well and proved themselves as promising configurations for prototype development. Additional simulations with tumor varieties provided supplementary information about benefits of the application of each arrangement for real clinical hyperthermia scenarios. In case of early stage neck cancer while the tumor size is varying between 1 and 2 cm or the tumor is generally located close to the surface of the neck, the ChCnf3 can be advantageous. Although, on the late stages or in case of esophagus or trachea cancer which have prolonged shape and larger dimensions (> 2 cm), ChCnf2 is more appropriate. In the future investigations, the hyperthermia applicators [3] are planned to be mounted in the experimental setup described in this paper and the performance of the channel configurations will be evaluated by measurements of temperature changes in the tumorous tissue.

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